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Spousal Communication and Male Involvement as Predictors of Women Contraceptive Use in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria, being one of the most populous countries among the black nations in the world is also amongst nations with the highest recorded cases of maternal and child deaths despite policies that supports and promotes contraceptive use. This paper assessed contraceptive use as an important strategy in promoting maternal and child health as it improves health through adequate spacing of births and avoiding pregnancy at high risk maternal ages and parity, unsafe abortion and has the potential to avert most maternal and child deaths. It explored the reasons for the low rates of contraceptive use despite the widespread knowledge and points out spousal communication and male involvement as key predictors of women contraceptive use. The paper suggests more emphasis on the benefits of contraceptive use, encourages spousal communication, advocates for the inclusion of males in family planning as well as training male family planning providers and developing convenient and short- term male contraceptives.

Keywords: contraceptive, family planning, spousal communication,

INTRODUCTION

Decades ago, contraceptive use was seen as a taboo in Nigeria and many other African countries. Children are seen as gifts from God and any attempt on birth control was considered sinful. This opinion has now changed and the idea of contraceptive use has come into play when people realized that the women needed to be relieved of the heavy load of frequent pregnancies and child bearing so as to enhance her longevity, and the need for adequate care and training for the children in the family. According to Azees, Ehiem, Isa, Awosan, and Suleiman (2022); World Family Planning (2022), family planning has proven to save and enhance the lives of women, children and families. It reduces the number of unintended, unwanted and mistimed pregnancies. Nevertheless, low rates of contraceptive use and high fertility rates persist in most countries of Sub - Saharan Africa where despite a rise in contraceptive prevalence, many women continue to have unmet need for contraception (Boadu, 2022; Kraft, Serbanescu, Schmitz, Mwanshemele, Ruiz C, Maro & Chaote, 2022).

Nigeria is one of the most populous countries in Sub – Saharan Africa, it has a population of 198 million people with a Total Fertility Rate (TFR) of 5.5 percent, and 2.54 percent growth rate (National Population Commission [NPC], 2018; National Agency for the Control of AIDS, 2015), Saddening to know also that the nation is among those nations with the highest recorded cases of maternal and child deaths despite the

various population policies that supports the provision and promotion of contraceptive use in the country. This is a clear indication that the widespread knowledge of contraceptives has not transcended to its use. Family planning (FP) is one of the most “health promoting” and cost effective activities in public health promotion and has the potential to avert approximately 30 percent of maternal and 10 percent of child deaths and also reduce the rate of unwanted pregnancies and abortions (Cleland, Conde-Agudelo, Peterson, Ross & Tsui, as cited in Umar, 2016). The current growth rate coupled with the economic situation of the country will bring about numerous consequences for reproductive health and the health of the populace in general if proper measures are not put in place.

Studies has shown that in some parts of Nigeria, one in five women report having experienced an unwanted conception, of these, 58 percent had an abortion and an additional 9 percent attempted unsuccessfully to end the pregnancy. It is estimated that about 25 percent of women who have abortion in Nigeria experience serious complications (Bankole, Adewole, Hussain, Awolude, Singh, & Akinyemi, 2015; Pasquier, Owolabi, Fetters, *et al.* 2023). Also, an estimated 500,000 women die of complications due to pregnancy, child bearing or unsafe abortion. Hence, it is evident that the adoption of family planning measures will reduce unwanted pregnancies and criminal abortions to its barest minimum.

Concept of contraceptive use

Contraceptive, synonymously used with family planning (FP) in this paper is the practice of controlling the number of children one has and the intervals between their births, particularly by means of contraception or voluntary sterilization (Hornby, 2000). This implies that it is the decision of people to have the desired number of children at their own time with the help of contraceptives. FP implies the ability of individuals and couples to anticipate and attain their desired number of children by spacing and timing their births. It is achieved through the use of contraceptive methods and the treatment of involuntary infertility. The availability of family planning does more than enable women and men to limit family size. It safeguards individual health and rights, and improves the quality of life of couples and their children.

The World Health Organization (WHO) as cited in Wani, Rashid, Nabi and Dar (2019) defined FP as a way of thinking and living adopted voluntarily upon the basis of knowledge, attitudes and responsible decisions by individuals and couples in order to promote the health of the family and thus contribute effectively to the social development of the country. This definition sees FP as a responsible decision made voluntarily by individuals and couples due to the knowledge they have acquired for the enhancement of family health thus, contribute meaningfully and participate effectively for the country’s development.

According to Planned Parenthood of America as cited in Peter-Kio (2020); Bansode, Sarao and Cooper (2023), contraceptive is any device or medication used for reducing the likelihood of fertilization of an ovum by spermatozoa, which could be obtained by temporal or permanent method or device. Contraceptive use according to World Health Organization (WHO) (2018) is the percentage of women who are currently using or whose partners are currently using at least one of the contraceptive method regardless of the methods used. Therefore, spousal contraceptive use is the percentage of wives(women) who are currently using at least one method of contraceptive as reported by their partner. In Nigeria, the proportion of women using contraceptives seems low. The 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey result showed that only 17 percent of Nigerians were currently using contraceptive (NPC, 2019). This low contraceptive use in Nigeria is a pointer to increase the total fertility rate of 5.5 which had also contributed to the increase in maternal mortality rate.

Family planning is an important strategy in promoting maternal and child health as it improves health through adequate spacing of births and avoiding pregnancy at high risk maternal ages and parities. The most important proximate determinant of fertility is the use of family planning (Stover & Winfrey, 2017) because where contraceptive use is widespread, fertility is low. Women who use contraceptive tend to have a better quality of life, higher social status, and greater autonomy. Asiimwe, Ndugga, Mushomi, Patrick and Ntozi, (2014) opined that FP is one of the most “health promoting” and cost-effective

activities in public health promotion and has the potential to avert most maternal and child deaths. Based on the aforementioned, the presenter holds the conviction that apart from creating awareness on FP, the influence of the predictors plays a key role on its usage.

Predictors of contraceptive use

Hornby (2012) defined predictor as something such as events or facts that enables you to say what will happen in the future. Predictor refers to something that determines the occurrence of a thing, something that indicates in advance either by observation, experience or scientific reason in order to foretell future occurrence. This paper establishes the fact that spousal communication and male involvement are a major predictor of women contraceptive use.

1. Spousal communication

Communication is a process of sharing information through a media and it is instrumental for marital satisfaction. Marital communication allows couples to discuss and share information that predicts and sustain contraceptive use. Communication could significantly predict spousal contraceptives use. In the study of Azmat, Ali, Ishaque et al. (2015) on assessing predictors of contraceptive use, communication was significantly associated with contraceptive use. In the same vein Sileo, Wanyenze, Luleet, et al. (2015) conducted a study on determinants of family planning service uptake and use of contraceptives among postpartum women in rural Uganda, result showed that communication significantly predicted contraceptive use. Studies had shown that marital communication significantly influenced and predicted the use of contraceptive (Olawole-Isaac, Oni, Oladosu, Amooet et al., 2017). Spousal communication predicts the use of contraceptives and the willingness of men to adopt or allow partners to use family planning to a large extent determines the pace of fertility reduction. Effective communication in marriage could enhance joint decision making, participation and gender balance more especially in the area of family planning and contraceptive use specifically. Communication can clear negative perceptions around the use of contraceptive and improves better parenthood and reproductive health outcome thereby increasing positive attitude towards contraceptive use (Peter-Kio, 2020).

Spousal communication in the marital dyad is generally defined as the frequency of discussion between spouses as reported by one or both partners (Link, 2011). This refers to how often marital partners discuss in relation to contraceptive use. Contraceptive use is found to be higher among those who had discussed about FP with each other (Zelalem, Worku, Alemayehu & Dessie, 2021). In a study conducted by Islam, Alam and Hasan (2024), results show that the contraception use rate was higher among couples (50.3%) who had favorable spousal communication compared to those (67.4%) who had unfavorable spousal communication. couples who had inter - spousal communication were 17.3 times more likely to use contraceptives compared to those that had no inter – spousal communication about family planning. This is in line with Link (2011) who investigated the relationship between spousal communication and contraceptive use and found out that increased spousal communication regarding FP significantly influences subsequent fertility - limiting behaviour. Based on these influences of spousal communication in marital relationship, spousal communication can be said to be a predictor of contraceptive use.

2. Male involvement

Male involvement is referred to as ways in which men relate to reproductive health problem, reproductive rights and reproductive behaviour (Dereje, Abainew, Abdlfatal, Abdo, Abdurazak & Kanenus, 2016). Also, Green and Chen (2003) explained that male involvement in FP means more than just increasing the number of men who encourage and support their partners and their peers to use FP. In this context, male involvement should not be regarded as male contraception, rather, it should be seen as all activities aimed at men as a discrete group which have the objective of increasing the acceptability and prevalence of FP practice of either sex. Studies have shown that involving men increased their contraceptive use, encouraged women's use of contraception, and improved continuation rates, on the other hand, women who use contraception without the knowledge or consent of their partners are more likely to discontinue use compared to those whose partners are involved in the decision to use a method because many women discontinue contraceptives to please their husbands (Akoth, Oguta & Gatimu, 2021). Kamal (2000) in his

study found out that a husband's disapproval leads to reduction in contraception as reproductive health programmes are likely to be more effective for women when men are actively involved.

Male involvement refers to all organizational initiatives addressed at men as a distinct category to enhance the acceptance and prevalence of contraceptive use in the family by both sexes. Second, increasing the number of men who encourage and support their partners and peers to use contraceptives, as well as their attitude toward family planning. Third, increasing the number of men who encourage and support their partners and peers to use contraceptives (Bayray, 2012; Shisoka & Litali, 2015). Male involvement in family planning, according to Mburu and Adams (2011) encompasses all efforts aimed at ensuring active participation. Male involvement in family planning also entails shared responsibility between couples in family planning topics, to allow for collaborative contraceptive decision-making. Male engagement in family planning has two sides, with men providing adequate assistance in times of need and choices.

Male involvement has been demonstrated to predict contraceptive use in studies. From these studies, male involvement plays an important role in the prediction of contraceptive use. Male engagement in family planning is measured by spouse approval and communication. The use of contraception is predicted by spouse approval of family planning. Also, men's involvement in FP is vital for policy and programs that aim to advance the achievement of FP goals in Africa. Hence, numerous studies and FP interventions have recommended that male involvement be incorporated into FP programs (Bhatt, Bhatt, Neupane, Karki, Bhatta, Thapa, Basnet, & Budhathoki, 2021). In a study conducted by Abraham, Adamu and Derese (2010), respondents who agreed with family planning were 16.6 times more likely to use contraceptives than those who did not approve of family planning. Kassa, Abajohir and Gedefew (2014) found that spouse approval affects the likelihood of using contraceptives as much as any other factor. Spousal support has been shown to predict contraceptive use as an indicator of male involvement in family planning. According to a study by Mekonnen and Worku (2011), women who have a supportive relationship are more likely to use contraception than women who do not have a supportive partner. Partners' support was substantially connected with contraceptive use, Ezeanolue, Iwelunmor, Asaolu, Obiefume, Ezeanolue, Osuji, Ogidi, Hunt, Patel, Yang and Ehiri (2015).

The finding of the study of Peter – Kio (2021) revealed a significant relationship between male involvement in family planning spousal contraceptive use. This is expected as more women in traditional African society depend on their male partners for livelihood. Thus, the more support from male partners the more likely will the female adopt the uptake of contraceptives. This finding is in keeping with the finding of Muema (2016) in Kenya where there was a significant relationship between spousal approval and contraceptive use. The finding of the study is also similar to the finding of Kama, et al, (2016) in rural Northern Nigeria where partner support is significantly related to contraceptive use.

In a research conducted by the Inainkon (2018), on predictors of contraceptive use, it was revealed that women who discussed contraceptive use with their spouse are 6.1 times likely to use contraceptives compared to those who did not discuss. It also indicates that women whose spouse were involved were 1.3 times more likely to use contraceptives compared to those whose spouse were not involved. Hence, the conviction that spousal communication and male involvement in contraceptive use are vital predictors of women's contraceptive use

CONCLUSION

This paper has explored Family planning as one of the most health promoting and cost effective activities in public health promotion which has the potential to avert approximately 30 percent of maternal and 10 percent of child deaths and also reduce the rate of unwanted pregnancies and abortions. Unfortunately, the proportion using contraceptives is low despite the widespread knowledge as many women still have unmet need for family planning hence efforts should not only be focused on knowledge rather it should encourage spousal communication which can enhance joint decision making and improve better parenthood and reproductive health, and inclusion of males as partners in reproductive health issues since they make major decisions including ones that has to do with women's reproductive health. With the

current growth rate coupled with the economic situation of the country, there is need to encourage contraceptive use as to help in reducing unnecessary hardship in various households

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the observations in this paper and the conclusion drawn, the following were suggested:

1. There is a need to increase awareness on the benefits of contraceptive to the mother, father, children, community and the country at large.
2. Information, Education and communication (IEC) campaigns on contraceptive use should encourage spousal communication to help foster joint decision making about reproductive health.
3. Advocate for inclusion of males as discrete partners to improve contraceptive use.
4. Training for male family planning providers and setting of male friendly reproductive health clinics.
5. Efforts should be made to improve family planning practices by developing convenient and short-term male contraceptives.

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